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Technical note on diffraction/far field SEDF

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<p>In this Technical note the effect of diffraction (SEDF far-field) with respect to CAIRT radiances is simulated and first LPE-uncertainty calculations on L2 temperature uncertainty are performed regarding far-field knowledge uncertainty.</p>		
<p>The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the contents resides with the author(s) or organisation(s) that prepared it.</p>		
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V1.0	19-Apr-2024	Initial version
V2.0		Add plots at 95 km, for different atmospheres, and radiance profiles around 720 cm-1 and 4 cm aperture size.
V3.0		More plots added in attachment zip-file: July+80 atmosphere, Dx=4 and 6 cm; log-radiance axis;
V4.0	5-Jul-2024	Add chapter on effects on temperature retrieval
V5.0	10-Oct-2025	Final adaptations due to comments on DEL-09-CAIRT-... related to far-field SEDF by Alex Hoffmann

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1 Introduction

The effect of diffraction with respect to CAIRT radiances is simulated.

2 Diffraction pattern of rectangular aperture

For the Fraunhofer diffraction pattern of intensity $I(x,y)$ for a rectangular slit of width D_x [cm] and height D_y [cm] is given as

(e.g. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fraunhofer_diffraction_equation#Rectangular_aperture):

$$I(x,y) \propto \text{sinc}^2(\pi\sigma D_x \sin x) \text{sinc}^2(\pi\sigma D_y \sin y)$$

Where σ is the wavenumber [cm^{-1}] and x,y [rad] the angles relative to the aperture's normal direction.

Figure 1 shows the resulting vertical pattern for $D_y = 6$ cm aperture height. Mind that the sampling of y has to be sufficient since $\pi\sigma D_y$ is up to nearly 40000.

Figure 1 Diffraction pattern for rectangular aperture ($x=0$) in vertical (y) direction and $D_y=6$ cm (sampled at 100001 points) at different wavenumbers. The labels at the top axis denote the relative approximate tangent height. The legend includes the full-width at half maximum of each function.

3 Effect of diffraction on limb-radiance spectra

To simulate the effect of the diffraction pattern from Figure 1 on limb-spectra, typical pencil beam spectra calculated on basis of the ERS-database for April, 45N, daytime, have been used. Figure 2 - Figure 4 show the pencil-beam radiances in absolute units as well as relative to the NESR (threshold/breakthrough for the short-wavelength range) for different atmospheric situations. Also, the differences between the radiances convolved with the vertical diffraction function ($D_y = 4\text{cm}$) and the pencil-beam radiances are presented for different tangent altitudes. Here the different colours denote how far away from the centre, the diffraction function has been used. This shows from how far away, the radiance contributions at some tangent altitude stems. At low tangent altitudes, the main contributions come from the nearest neighbour pixels – an effect which is readily captured by the field-of-view function and its knowledge uncertainties accounted for by the SEDF uncertainty estimation for the inner FOV.

This picture is reversed for the high altitudes where the additional radiances from pixels far away contribute dominantly compared to the neighbouring ones (yellow/green vs. grey/pink curves) – an effect which has not been considered during SciReC. Wavenumber-wise the strongest influence at high altitudes appear in the CO₂ region below around 800 cm^{-1} and in the ozone-band at around 1000 cm^{-1} .

Radiance profiles at the CO₂-Q-branch at around 720 cm^{-1} as well as at a wavenumber beside are shown in Figure 5. The green line shows the difference between these two radiance profiles. For the Q-branch center, a maximum is reached at around 55 km below which it decreases since the atmosphere becomes opaque below.

Figure 6 shows the radiance profile for an aperture size $D_y = 4\text{ cm}$ instead of 6 cm.

For more radiance-plots regarding different atmospheres and aperture heights of 4 cm and 6 cm: see attachment figure-collection: [diffra_fig.zip](#)

Figure 2 Pencil-beam limb radiances (blue) and their differences to those convolved with the vertical diffraction function for $D_y=4$ cm (mind that D_x in the plots' title should read D_y) aperture height in absolute units (left) and

relative (in %) to the NESR (threshold/breakthrough for the short-wavelength range)(right) for different tangent altitudes. The different colours (apart from blue) denote how far away from the centre (in pixels of about 1 km tangent height), the diffraction function has been applied. Mind that '±1000pix' refers to the total vertical extension. Atmosphere: April+45_day.

Figure 3 Same as Figure 2 but for the short-wavelength range (mind that Dx in the plots' title should read Dy).

Figure 4 Zoom into Figure 2 (mind that Dx in the plots' title should read Dy).

Figure 5 Radiance profiles at two wavenumbers of April+45_day (mind that Dx in the plots' title should read Dy).

Figure 6 As Figure 5 but for an aperture height Dy= 6 cm (mind that Dx in the plots' title should read Dy).

4 Effect of diffraction knowledge on temperature retrieval

To simulate the effect of the knowledge of the far-field diffraction pattern on the retrieval, we calculated 'error-spectra' by including the far-field diffraction pattern of 4 cm aperture height in the instrument-simulator of the Ipe. The error-spectra are the difference between the reference run and the run where the far-field diffraction pattern is multiplied by a factor of 1.5. I.e. we assume a factor of 50% knowledge error over the region of the far-field.

The transition from the near to the far-field as used in the Ipe is shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8: in the central region up to $\pm 2 \times$ half-width of the central gaussian SEDF which is set to 1.4 km (not wavenumber dependent). Outside the central region, the SEDF is set to wavenumber-dependent diffraction function for an aperture height $D_y=4$ cm (Figure 9).

Figure 10 - Figure 15 show the retrieval results for different ERS-atmospheres in case the outer SEDF knowledge was distorted (Figure 11, Figure 13, Figure 15) compared to the reference case where only the inner SEDF knowledge was affected (1% half-width constant with altitude and 1% half-width random with altitude) (Figure 10, Figure 12, Figure 14). Mind that in the figures of the outer SEDF distortion, the NLTE and CO₂ uncertainty terms have not been evaluated. In the upper figures with the inner SEDF-knowledge uncertainty, the respective curves are so small that they are below the minimum plotted range. In comparison, the outer-SEDF 50% knowledge uncertainty (dark purple lines in the lower Figures of each page) affects the temperature retrieval at altitudes above about 60-70 km thereby often being the leading term of systematic uncertainty, comparable or even exceeding the NLTE uncertainties at high altitudes, especially in extreme atmospheric conditions like the summertime high-latitude atmospheres with extremely cold temperatures.

Figure 7 Transition between the inner SEDF (green) less than $\pm 2 \times$ FWHM(Gauss) and the diffraction curves (blue, orange). The used SEDF-functions are the dotted curves. The x-axis refers to the projection at 5 km tangent height.

Figure 8 Like Figure 7 but with logscale y-axis.

Figure 9 Like Figure 8 but showing the broad SEDF.

Figure 10 LPE error estimation for temperature 2d retrieval reference case where the inner part of the SEDF has been disturbed and is indicated as ‘SEDF knowledge’ in the legend. However, mind that this ‘SEDF knowledge’ uncertainty for the inner part of the SEDF is so small that it is below the x-axis plot limit. These error curves include ‘NLTE uncertainties’ and ‘CO₂ uncertainty’. Atmosphere: April+45_day.

Figure 11 LPE error estimation for temperature 2d retrieval diffraction case where only the outer (diffraction) part of the SEDF was distorted by 50% knowledge error: dark purple ‘SEDF knowledge’ curve. Mind that here ‘NLTE uncertainties’ and ‘CO₂ uncertainty’ are not included, but incorrectly displayed in the legend. Atmosphere: April+45_day.

Figure 12 As

Figure 10 but for atmosphere: January+80_night.

Figure 13 As Figure 11 but for atmosphere: January+80_night.

Figure 14 As

Figure 10 but for atmosphere: July+80_day.

Figure 15 As Figure 11 but for atmosphere: July+80_day.